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ABSTRACT BOOK

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«Geosciences for the environment,
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From quarrying site to geosite: a review on a possible approach to project an open-air museum as a key to preserve geological data

Rossi F.P.*¹, Madonna S.¹ & Milli S.²

¹ Università degli Studi della Tuscia - Dipartimento di Scienze e Tecnologie per l'Agricoltura le Foreste la Natura e l'Energia, Viterbo

² Sapeinza, Università di Roma - Dipartimento di Scienze della Terra, Roma

* *Corresponding email:* fg.rossi@unitus.it

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Many quarrying sites at the end of the activity are covered and re-natured through a morphological land modeling and a subsequent re-vegetation (environmental restoration). However these actions are very expensive and rarely effective, and in some cases risk to cover unique features emerging on the excavation fronts. In the last few decades, landscapes and geological features of depleted mining sites start to be considered as a resource with a public value that could attract a new generation of culturally and scientifically oriented tourists. However, to be fully effective, planning the functional recovery should take place in parallel with the exploitation activities.

Facies analysis could be a useful tool to ameliorate an overall knowledge on sedimentary stone materials, helping improving marketability, reducing the volumes of waste and collect data to plan a future open-air museum. Here we present a quarrying site in Tuscany (Italy), Poggio la Vecchia quarry. The extracted lithotype, well-known in literature as Manciano sandstone, consists of medium-coarse sands with local intercalations of conglomerates, which were deposited in shallow-water environment (see Rossi et al., 2017 with references therein). Some of the well exposed, diamond-line cut, allow a detailed analysis of textures and sedimentary structures, as well as ichnofacies, fossils, etc.; in this study, we also obtained HD orthophotoimages and a detailed morphological model using UAV flights. A huge stock of data and about 1000 detailed pictures took with a HD GPS built-in Camera were also collected and geolocated.

For its central position in the Tuscany area and the height of the mining site (more than 80m in 12 climbing walls), Poggio la Vecchia quarry represents an incredible opportunity to “read history” on every wall, of every step of the quarry. All this deserve to be preserved and turned into a Geosite. This lithotype is very stable geotechnically allowing the site to easily be converted in a visiting site, operational facilities in indoor museum areas and wasting sites in picnic areas following an environmental rehabilitation.

Exploitation and recovery plan to be submitted (L.R. Toscana n°35/2015) lasts 25 years. This timeframe is adequate to collect enough data throughout the lifespan of Poggio La Vecchia quarry.

Rossi, F.G., Madonna, S. & Milli, S. (2017): “Facies analysis applied to quarrying” a review of the possible use of sedimentology to increase knowledge and use of ornamental sandstones. *Procedia Engineering*, 208, 136-144.

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